

SELECTIVE EXTRACTION-PHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR DETERMINING COPPER ECOTOXICANT WITH 1- (2-PYRIDYLAZO) -2-NAPHTHOL (PAN)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17186963>

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Abstract. *As is known, many chemical compounds and toxic metals, as a result of the work of enterprises, plants, and factories, with atmospheric precipitation, dissolve in moisture droplets as pollutants and enter the soil and water. Considering the increasing scale of production and application of heavy toxic metals, their high toxicity and carcinogenicity, the ability to accumulate in the human body, and even in low concentrations, to exert harmful effects. Such ecotoxicants also include copper, cadmium, nickel, and others. Therefore, the relevance of the presented work is evident and relevant. The search for selective ecoanalytical methods for determining ecotoxicants in materials with complex chemical composition is a pressing task. Modern ecoanalytical analysis methods, such as chromato-spectrometry, chromato-mass spectrometry, atomic absorption, plasma, X-ray fluorescence, and others, do not always allow for the solution of this problem due to the complexity and limited availability of equipment.*

Keywords: *high toxicity, harmful effects, ecoanalytical methods, X-ray fluorescence, atomic absorption, plasma.*

Introduction

Existing photometric and extraction-photometric methods for determining copper using azoreagents are not sufficiently selective [1, 2], as the complexation of copper (II) with azoreagents is carried out in an aqueous solution. In this case, many accompanying ions form colored compounds with the indicated reagents and are extracted together with copper. The selectivity of copper (II) ion determination by pyridine oxazo compounds is enhanced by preliminary extraction of copper (II) ions by salicylaldoxime to separate them from accompanying elements [3]. This method is also insufficiently selective, moreover, it is long-term and inaccurate, as this

methodology involves re-extraction after preliminary extraction, then extraction again, with inevitable losses.

In this work, a new, selective, and simple method based on the extraction of a colorless copper (II) iodide complex with inert organic solvents and its complex formation with PAN directly in the organic phase is discussed.

Experiments have shown that copper (II) from a solution containing sulfuric acid, iodide ions, and dimethylformamide (DMFA) is selectively extracted with chloroform. According to the data of copper (II) extraction with chloroform, depending on the concentration of sulfuric acid, iodide ions and DMFA, the optimal condition is: 2-4 M H₂SO₄; 0.08–0.2 M iodide ions and 25-40 vol.% DMFA (by volume). The shaking time of the phases is 10-15 seconds. With equal volumes of aqueous and organic phases, copper (II) is extracted by 99% unchanged to a phase volume ratio of 3:1. The composition of the extracted copper (II) iodide complex was determined by the equilibrium shift method [4].

The results of the obtained data showed that in the biloharithmic coordinates: $\lg D_{Cu^{+2}} - \lg C_{H^+}$, $\lg D_{Cu^{+2}} - \lg C_{I^-}$, $\lg D_{Cu^{+2}} - \lg C_{DMFA}$ (where D is the distribution coefficient, C is the equilibrium concentration), a linear relationship is observed with tangents of the angle of inclination of the lines, respectively equal to 2, 4, 4 (Table. 1, Fig. 1).

Determination of the number of hydrogen ions, iodide ions of DMFA participating in the extraction of copper with chloroform ($A_{pr}=0,53$; $C_{Cu}=1,89 \cdot 10^{-4}$)

$C_{H_2SO_4}, M$	A	$D = \frac{A}{pr - A}$	$\lg D$	$-\lg C_{H_2SO_4}, equal.$	
0,5	0,330	1,524	0,183	0,301	
0,7	0,360	2,120	0,326	0,155	
1,0	0,390	2,78	0,45	0,000	
1,2	0,41	3,15	0,498	-0,079	
1,5	0,44	4,88	0,689	-0,176	
2,0	0,46	6,53	0,818	-0,301	
C_{NaI}, M	A	$D = \frac{A}{A_{pr} - A}$	$\lg D$	$-\lg C_{NaI}$	
0,06	0,225	0,6923	-0,160	1,22	
0,08	0,328	1,4774	0,169	1,09	
0,10	0,410	2,9285	0,467	1,00	
0,12	0,460	5,111	0,70	0,921	
0,14	0,510	12,7500	1,105	0,854	
0,16	0,525	22,0000	1,342	0,796	
C_{DMFA}, M	A	$D = \frac{A}{A_{np} - A}$	$\lg D$	$-\lg C_{DMFA}$	K_s
0,1324	0,167	0,450	-0,3372	0,880	54,34
0,2648	0,332	1,677	0,2246	0,580	47,83
0,3972	0,350	1,944	0,4487	0,450	24,64
0,5296	0,440	4,889	0,6892	0,276	37,78
0,6620	0,468	7,548	0,8779	0,179	34,45
0,7944	0,480	9,600	0,9823	0,100	30,42

0,9268	0,500	16,667	1,2221	0,080	38,80
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Fig. 1. Determination of the number of hydrogen ions, iodide ions of DMFA participating in the extraction of copper by chloroform.

Therefore, copper (II) is extracted by chloroform in the form of $H_2 [CuI_4]$; the solvation number in the extract is 4. The number of water molecules associated with the copper complex ion in the extract, determined by the Fisher method [5], is 4.

Based on experimental data, it seems that the copper (II) iodide complex from acidic solutions in the presence of DMFA is extracted by chloroform according to the hydrate-solvate mechanism [4]:

where L_o is chloroform.

After extraction of copper (II) under optimal conditions, separation of the aqueous phase, addition to the extract of PAN chloroform solution, buffer solution, and shaking of the phases for 30-40 seconds, copper (II) interacts with PAN. It has been established that the complete complexation of copper (II) with PAN in the organic phase occurs in the pH range of 8.5-11.

By the method of equilibrium shifting [6], it has been established that copper (II) interacts with PAN in the organic phase in a molar ratio of 1:2 at low concentrations and 1:4 at high concentrations (Table. 2, Fig. 2).

Table 2.

Determination of the molar ratio of copper (II) and PAN by the method of equilibrium shift during extraction with chloroform ($A_{pr}=0,53$; $C_{Cu}=1,89 \cdot 10^{-4}$)

C_{PAN}, M	A	$D = \frac{A}{A_{pr} - A}$	$lg D$	$-lg C_{PAN}, equiv.$
35,50	0,03	0,093	-1,028	2,452
53,25	0,08	0,296	-0,528	2,275
71,00	0,15	0,750	-0,124	2,15
88,75	0,19	1,187	0,074	2,053
106,50	0,17	3,375	0,528	1,974

124,20	0,30	6,000	0,778	1,907
142,50	0,32	10,000	1,028	1,849
159,70	0,34	34,000	1,53	1,798

Fig. 2. Determination of the molar ratios of copper (II) and PAN by the equilibrium shift method during extraction with chloroform. Consequently, the copper (II) complexation reaction with PAN in the organic phase can be represented abbreviatedly by the scheme:

The complex of copper (II) with PAN in chloroform is stable for more than 3 days. The apparent molar attenuation coefficient of the copper-PAN complex at the maximum light absorption $\lambda_{max}=560$ nm is $2.8 \cdot 10^4$. The copper-PAN complex obeys the Beer law in the range of 1-160 μ g of copper in 10 ml of extract. The reproducibility of determination is within 1-5%.

Under copper (II) extraction conditions, bismuth, mercury, cadmium, palladium, platinum, and zinc ions are partially extracted. However, under the conditions of copper complex formation with PAN in the organic phase, bismuth, palladium, cadmium, and platinum ions do not form complexes with PAN and do not interfere with the determination. The interfering effects of zinc ions are eliminated by washing the 10 ml extract once with a mixture containing 2 M H_2SO_4 , 0.5 M rhodanide ions, and 30 vol. % DMFA. The influence of many foreign ions was also studied, in which large multiples did not interfere with the determination (Table. 3). Alkali and alkaline earth elements, fluorides, chlorides, bromides, nitrates, rhodanides, thiosulfates, thiourea, tartaric and ascorbic acids do not interfere with the determination of copper (II). The method of determining the copper iodide complex in the presence of DMFA with subsequent addition of a reagent is also promising because, by selecting reagents, it is possible to significantly increase the sensitivity of photometric determinations.

Table 3.

Selectivity of copper (II) iodide complex with PAN during extraction with chloroform (10 mcg of copper was taken)

M	M/Cu	M/Cu	M/Cu
Ag (I)	400	Th (IV)	1000
Tl (I)	400	Pt (IV)	1000
Zn (II)	1000 ¹	V (V)	1000

Pb (II)	250	Nb (V)	2500
Mn (II)	5000	W (VI)	2000 ²
Cd (II)	300	Te (VI)	1000
Hg (II)	100	Mo (VI)	1000
Ca (II)	5000	U (VI)	1000
Ba (II)	5000	Os (VIII)	200
Mg (II)	5000	F ⁻	3000
Pd (II)	500	Cl ⁻	4000
Be (II)	10000	NO ₃ ⁻	10000
Co (II)	10000	PO ₄ ⁻³	5000
Ni (III)	5000	C ₂ O ₄ ⁻²	2000
Fe (III)	500	CH ₃ COO ⁻	3000
Al (III)	5000	S ₂ O ₃ ⁻²	1000
Au (III)	400	Tartaric acid	doesn't interfere
Bi (III)	2000	Ascorbic	5000
Rh (III)	2000	acid	3000
In (III)	5000	La (III)	1000
Ga (III)	1000	Ti (IV)	1000
Cr (III)	2000	Zr (IV)	10000
Ag (III)	1000	Se (IV)	2000

M - ion or compound; M/Cu - permissible ratio to copper by mass; 1 - after a single washing of the extract with 10 ml of a solution containing 2 M H₂SO₄, 0,5 M KCNS, and 30 vol. % DMFA; 2 - when 100 mg of tartaric acid was added to the extraction mixture.

Determination of copper in pure solutions and in the presence of foreign ions

An analyzed solution containing 1-160 µg of copper (II) is introduced into a 25 ml volumetric cylinder with a ground stopper, 3 ml of 5 M H₂SO₄ is added, diluted with water to 6 ml, 1 ml of 1 M NaJ containing 2% ascorbic acid (to prevent oxidation of iodide ions), 3 ml DMFA, 5 ml chloroform are added and shaken for 10-15 sec. The extract is separated by a separating funnel, and 0.05% PAN chloroform solution, 5 ml of ammonia buffer solution with pH=10 are added to the extract and shaken for 30-40 seconds. The resulting colored complex in the extract is filtered through filter paper and photometered relative to the free experimental solution.

In industrial samples and mineral raw materials, copper occurs in mixtures with many elements. To determine the possibility of determining copper from samples with a complex chemical composition, the influence of extraneous ions during the determination of copper with PAN was studied. The method for determining copper in the presence of foreign ions is the same as when determining it in pure solutions, with the only difference being that certain amounts of foreign ions or compounds were added to the solution being determined beforehand, and in some cases, masking agents were added as needed.

During the extraction of copper under optimal conditions, bismuth, mercury, cadmium, palladium, platinum, and zinc ions are partially extracted. However, under the conditions of copper (II) complexation with PAN in the organic phase, bismuth, palladium, cadmium, and platinum ions do not form complexes with PAN and do not interfere with the determination. The zinc ion interference is eliminated by washing the extract once with a 10 ml mixture containing 2 M H₂SO₄, 0.5 M rhodanide ions, and 30 vol.% DMFA.

The developed new method for extraction-spectrophotometric determination of copper (II) with PAN was tested in the analysis of dust, cakes (table 4), and wastewater from the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine, where the reproducibility of determination did not exceed 1-5%.

Table 4

Determination of copper in the wastewater of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Production with the reagent PAN (n=4; P=0.95)

Determination of copper in wastewater, mg/l	Copper found, \bar{x} mg/l	$S_r \cdot 10^2$	$\pm \Delta \bar{x} \cdot 10^2$	$\pm \frac{\Delta \bar{x}}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100$
6,00	5,80	0,940	8,70	1,50
15,00	15,10	0,867	20,84	1,38
21,00	20,50	0,321	10,46	0,51
37,00	36,80	1,326	77,65	2,11
52,00	52,30	1,113	92,57	1,77

Method for determining copper in dust and cakes with the reagent PAN

To determine copper in dust and cakes, a sample sample (1g) was placed in a 250 ml conical flask, 20 ml of HCl (l= 1.19) was added, heated in a sand bath for 10 minutes, 10 ml of nitric acid (l=1.4) was added, the mixture was evaporated to moist salts, and 20 ml of 0.5 m sulfuric acid solution was added. The precipitate after cooling was filtered into 100 ml volumetric flasks and diluted to the mark with 0.5 ml sulfuric acid solutions. From the aliquot portion (1-3 ml) of the solutions, copper was determined as in the analysis of copper from pure solutions.

Table 5

Determination of copper in dust and cakes of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Production with the reagent PAN (n=4; P=0.95)

Sample number	Honey content, %	Copper found (\bar{x})	$\Delta \bar{x} \cdot 10^4$	S_r	$\frac{\Delta \bar{x}}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100$
Passion -6 19763	0,0260	0,0267	$\pm 7,79$	0,018	$\pm 2,92$
Passion -6 17979	0,0260	0,0264	$\pm 4,10$	0,010	$\pm 1,58$
Cake 19969	0,0100	0,0102	$\pm 2,56$	0,016	$\pm 2,51$
Cake 19970	0,0270	0,0279	$\pm 4,14$	0,016	$\pm 1,48$
Cake 17983	0,0220	0,0216	$\pm 5,03$	0,015	$\pm 2,32$

Method for determining copper in ores with PAN reagent

Considering the low copper content in the hands ($\approx 10-3\%$) for analysis, we took a sample of 4 g of ore, placed in a 250 ml conical flask, added 60 ml of HCl (sl=1.19) and heated for 10 minutes, added 30 ml of nitric acid (sl=1.40), evaporated to a volume of 30 ml, then added 20 ml of sulfuric acid (1:1) and heated to weak sulfur anhydride vapors, then added 50 ml of water, heated to boiling, cooled, filtered through a dense filter into a 100 ml volumetric flask, and diluted with water to the mark. From the aliquot portion (2-3 ml) of the solution, copper was determined

as in the analysis of copper from pure solutions. The copper content was determined from the calibration graph (Table 6).

Table 6

Determination of copper in the ores of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Production with the reagent PAN (n=4; P=0.95)

Name and sample number	Copper content in passport, %	Copper found (\bar{x}) 10^3 %	$\Delta\bar{x} \cdot 10^5$	$S_r \cdot 10^2$	$\frac{\Delta\bar{x}}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100$
Ore: 495	1,108	1,102	$\pm 4,740$	2,702	$\pm 4,30$
Ore: 496	1,836	1,829	$\pm 8,230$	2,828	$\pm 4,50$
Ore: 497	1,614	1,626	$\pm 5,85$	2,253	$\pm 3,60$

Conclusion

Thus, the developed new method of extraction-spectrophotometric determination of copper with PAN can be recommended for the analysis of ores, concentrates, industrial solutions, wastewater, dust, cakes, and other materials of complex chemical composition without separation of associated elements.

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